

ExtremeXP

Experiment Driven and user Experience Oriented Analytics for Extremely Precise Outcomes and Decisions

D2.1: Initial architecture, languages and models for complex experiment-driven analytics

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Abstract	This deliverable presents the modelling language and the initial design of the architecture of the ExtremeXP framework. It first presents the main concepts and the overall approach towards a next-generation experimentation framework. It introduces a novel meta-model describing the experimentation process for optimizing complex analytics as well as a probabilistic approach, which complements the meta-model, by providing assurances, options ranking, and verification of ExtremeXP configurations. It then provides the foundations for the trustworthiness and traceability layer and final presents the initial software architecture of the ExtremeXP framework.
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List of Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
ABAC	Attribute-based Access Control
API	Application Programming Interface
AutoML	Automated Machine Learning
BN	Bayesian network
BPMN	Business Process Model and Notation
CAW	Complex Analytic Workflow
CH	Context Handler
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
DPA	Data Processing Agreements
DSML	Domain Specific Modelling Language
EMF	Eclipse Modelling Framework
ETH	Ether
ETL	Extract-Transform-Load
GPU	Graphical Processing Unit
IPFS	Inter Planetary File System
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
GDPR	General data protection regulation
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
MDP	Markov Decision Process
NFT	Non-Fungible Token
OMG	Object Management Group
PAP	Policy Administration Point
PEP	Policy Enforcement Point
PDP	Policy Decision Point
PIP	Policy Information Point
QoS	Quality of Service
RPC	Remote Procedure Call
RTX	Real-Time Experimentation
SPOF	Single point of failure

UI	User Interface
UML	Unified Modelling Language
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
vCPU	Virtual Central Processing Unit
vRAM	Virtual Random Access Memory
WP	Work package
XACML	Extensible Access Control Markup Language
XML	Extensible Markup Language

Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on the activities of WP2 Conceptual foundations for experiment-driven analytics over extreme data (M1-M24), which is led by UL, with major contributions from the partners VUA, CUNI, TUDelft, ICOM and UPC. It represents our initial iteration of the architecture and its rationale, while the final architecture, language and models will be presented in D2.2 in M36.

The goal of our activities in the first project year has been to provide the initial modelling and language foundations for experiment-driven analytics focusing on software variability aspects, experiment specification, and context. This deliverable also provides the foundations for the trustworthiness and traceability layer and the software architecture of the ExtremeXP framework. This deliverable is designed to feed all the other technical work packages, i.e., WP3-5.

The initial Section 1 sets the scene by analyzing the main objectives of the modelling work and aligning our approach with the overall objectives of the project. Section 2 then provides definitions and an approach towards a next-generation experimentation framework that operates based on fit-for-purpose and human-in-the-loop principles.

In Section 3 we report on the activities of Task 2.1: Experimentation modelling with domain specific modelling languages, which was led by CUNI. The section focuses on the development of the foundational and novel meta-model and the associated Domain Specific Modelling Language (DSML) describing the experimentation process for optimizing complex analytics. DSML (defined with Eclipse EMF) will allow the specification of different variants of a complex analytics process to be mapped to a user-specified intent and context (T4.3); such variants include different datasets/data sources, the flow of complex analytics tasks (visualization, simulation, ML), deployment options, algorithms, models, hyper-parameters. It will also allow the specification of key metrics of experiment properties (e.g., time, resources, model accuracy) and their hypothesized difference that allows for their evaluation, comparison, planning and re-planning at runtime. The language developed in Task 2.1 will be used by the experimentation engine of T5.1 and the monitoring facilities of T5.2.

In Section 4 we report on the activities of Task 2.2: Semantically rich context representation and probabilistic meta-analysis, which is led by UL. Essentially, what is presented is our initial probabilistic Markov Decision Processes and Bayesian Network models that are designed to complement the meta-model described under Section 3. Focus is placed on the solution to provide assurances, options ranking, and verification of ExtremeXP configurations. This way, we establish association rules between users and configurations. This work will further be used by the Adaptive Experiment Planning of T5.1. This activity is also designed to inform the formalism for specifying user intents in T4.3 and the models that will be used under T4.4.

Section 5 reports on the activities of Task 2.3 Traceability and trustworthiness for experiment-driven analytics, which is led by TUDelft. The aim is to register access to data and their contextual circumstances that control access to data and knowledge artefacts, even across organizational boundaries. This task builds on the Attribute-based Access Control (ABAC) model and it designs and extends the attribute-based access control mechanism (T5.4) based on smart contracts provisioning over a private and permissioned blockchain. Moreover, a Non-Fungible Token (NFT)-based dataset provenance mechanism is presented, which is used for transparently, immutably, and uniquely 'tagging' the datasets used for experiment-driven analytics with metadata. The outcome of this work will be integrated into the framework's holistic data and knowledge management and lifecycle support (T5.5).

Finally, Section 6 describes the results of Task 2.4: Software and reference architecture for complex experiment-driven analytics, which is led by VUA. Here, we focus on the software architecture of the ExtremeXP framework. The architecture is presented in structural and behavioural diagrams. It

consists of several independent, self-contained, and elastic components that can be used to store knowledge assets from experiments, collect evaluation data including user feedback, plan experiments, and enact them (either locally or on remote systems) using virtualized resources and serverless functions. It supports scheduling and running several experiment variants (alternative configurations of a complex analytics process) in parallel. The core services of the framework will be implemented in WP5. The architecture provides interfaces between the different support services, i.e., data, algorithm, model, and feature selection services of WP3 and explainability, visualization, and human-in-the-loop services of WP4, to the Adaptive Experiment Planning (T5.1).

1 Introduction

Extreme data characteristics - including immense volume, rapid velocity, diverse heterogeneity, wide distribution, varying quality, and more - significantly strain current data-driven analytics and decision-making methods across crucial domains like crisis management, predictive maintenance, mobility, public safety, and cyber-security. The demand for data-driven insights amplifies the necessity for utmost **timeliness, accuracy, precision, suitability, and trustworthiness** to ensure their practical utility. To address these challenges, **ExtremeXP** aims to navigate the intricate landscape of extreme requirements through sophisticated analytics processes. These processes, integrating **machine learning, data analysis, simulation, and visualization** components, prioritize the end user's role, leveraging **user intents** and **iterative experimentation** ('trial and error') to streamline the extensive solution space encompassing diverse analytics workflows and configurations - known as 'variants.' The core objective is to pioneer a **next-generation decision support system** by amalgamating pioneering research outcomes from diverse domains: data integration, machine learning, visual analytics, explainable AI, decentralized trust, knowledge engineering, and model-driven engineering. This unified framework aims to redefine decision-making paradigms for handling extreme data challenges. In summary, the ExtremeXP framework is a collection of interacting software components and related databases and repositories provided by the ExtremeXP partners.

WP2 is a work package that aims to establish the **modelling and language foundations** for the experiment-driven analytics in ExtremeXP. WP2 focuses on software variability, experiment specification, and experiment context. It also provides the foundations for the trustworthiness and traceability layer, which ensures the secure and safe access management by using decentralised ledger technologies. Moreover, this work package defines the software architecture of the ExtremeXP framework, which integrates the different components and tools for experiment-driven analytics. The output from WP2 is utilised by all other technical work packages WP3-WP5.

This deliverable **D2.1** reports on the activities and the output of WP2 within the first year of the project. The activities under WP2 started by performing deep analysis of the ExtremeXP use cases and their requirements in relation to the overall objectives of the project. All tasks under WP2 reflected on the analyzed requirements, and provided their initial approach, particularly, related to the meta-model, the model of the probabilistic processes, and the blockchain-based access control mechanisms.

During this process, several key questions were discussed, including:

- What are the generic requirements that must be addressed by the architecture?
 - o These include the requirements for human-in-the-loop and accuracy/precision (fit-for-purpose).
 - o The framework must be designed as opinion-neutral towards its users.
- What concepts are to be included in the initial meta-model?
 - o Particularly, related to user intentions, goals, objectives, visualization of results and similar.
 - o Modularity of the initial meta-model should allow for its graceful extension in the future.
- What are the levels of abstraction that must be addressed?
 - o Here, it is obvious that all abstraction levels may apply, hence, the model should not be restrained to a few abstraction levels.
- Which is the most effective formalism that can be used to develop the knowledge base?
 - o Mainstream formalisms and models, such as Resource Description Framework (RDF) and Web Ontology Language (OWL), may be most useful and would allow for integration of the solution with various systems in the future.
- What are the appropriate meta-models for the probabilistic decision-making processes and the ABAC?

- While an initial approach has been agreed, more work is necessary in the next period to finalize the modelling under Tasks T2.2 and T2.3. Initial software has been designed to address the ABAC approach under T2.3.

The following is a brief account of how the overall project objectives were addressed during these activities.

O1: Specification and semantics for modelling complex user-experience-driven analytics

Under T2.1 initial meta-models were developed to capture the variability in complex analytics, the data to be collected to evaluate system properties and user feedback, and user requirements and preferences. Under T2.2 an initial probabilistic process was designed that considers Markov Decision Model and Bayesian Networks approach to allow for formal specification, ranking and verification of analytics processes. These activities took special care to include both the quality of service (QoS) and user experience metrics in the modelling process.

O2: Automated and scalable data management for complex analytics workflows

The meta-model designed under T2.1 may be used to facilitate automated discovery, selection, cleaning, deduplication, and augmentation techniques for data integration from dispersed, heterogeneous, and multi-lingual data sources of varying quality and format. The meta-model may also be used to generate datasets via simulations so that the accuracy of the models (by precise selection of training data) is enhanced. In the following stages of the project, we shall consider the development of methods for parallelization and distribution of complex (ML and data analytics) workflows, adapting to data source properties and infrastructure resource availability with the goal to scale and speed up ML and analytics workflows.

O3: Scenario-driven and opportunistic machine learning

The ExtremeXP knowledge base is designed to operate under the closed-world assumption. This is mainly exemplified through the activities under Task 2.2. It will allow the user to specify constraints that can be used to narrow down and select an existing Complex Analytic Workflow (CAW) or start the design process from scratch. This will allow the development of AutoML (Automated Machine Learning) mechanisms for performing scenario-based algorithm and model selection considering on-demand user-provided constraints (performance, resources, time, model options).

The Markov Decision Process and Bayesian Networks that are used under T2.2 represent mechanisms that can also be used for continual learning in algorithm and model selection: as new data sets become available, the so-far learned selection strategies are adapted and not learned from scratch, saving resources.

O4: User-experience- and experiment-driven optimization of complex analytics

Task T2.4 focused on the design of a framework architecture for experiment-driven optimization of complex analytics. The architecture contains an experimentation engine for optimizing complex analytics processes. This module learns which complex analytics variant (i.e., alternative complex analytics process) is best suited for each user's intent and context via conducting experiments involving users (like A/B testing).

O5: Transparent decision making with interactive visualisation methods

The architecture designed under Task T2.4 also contains an approach for the visualization of the results that includes humans-in-the-loop. It will utilize augmented reality, visual analytics, and other visualisation techniques and their combinations, as well as explanations to enhance the user experience for different use cases, actors, domains, applications, and problem areas.

O6: Extreme data access control and knowledge management

This objective is addressed mainly through the activities of Task T2.3. This task designed a novel blockchain-based Attribute Based Access Control (ABAC) paradigm for enabling seamless access to data sources, datasets, outputs as well as experimentation process metadata. ABAC is extended by incorporating contextual information capable of distinguishing e.g., the intended use of data in an experiment. Initial distributed ledger and smart contract-based methods for defining and transparently registering access control to experiment data and for using context to drive the permit decisions across organizations, were designed and are presented.

2 Foundational Concepts of ExtremeXP

2.1 Main concepts

The ExtremeXP approach aims at supporting the development and operation of complex (in terms of the nature of the operation and their scope) analytics workflows that are used for taking data-driven decisions in different application domains. Its motivation is, on the one hand, the dire need for decision making based on accurate, precise, fit-for-purpose, and trustworthy data-driven insights; on the other hand, the fact that existing R&D efforts typically target only one of the aspects of the data analytics conundrum: they focus either on resource efficiency and scalability, data management, ML performance, AI explainability, or data visualization. In response to this, ExtremeXP proposes *experimentation-driven analytics*, a new paradigm for data analytics that it puts the end user, i.e., requirements, preferences, constraints, interpretation, explanations, feedback, and decision making, at the centre of complex analytics processes (from data discovery to novel interactions).

To do so, it relies on several key concepts, namely:

Complex Analytics Workflow (CAW). It is an abstraction over different types of data-driven analytics workflows that includes (possibly combinations of):

- machine learning (ML) lifecycle workflows, which can be materialized via state-of-the-art AutoML and Machine Learning Operations (MLOps) solutions such as MLFlow;
- job scheduling and task automation workflows, which can be materialized in Activeeon's ProActive tool;
- simulation-based workflows, i.e., chaining of simulation models;
- data analysis scripts, as developed, e.g., by data analysts using notebooks;
- extract-transform-load (ETL) pipelines found in data warehousing technologies;
- scientific workflows like what can be developed with, e.g., Apache Taverna.

ExtremeXP experiment. Experiments are used within ExtremeXP to systematically develop, automate, reuse, setup, execute, track, explain, compare, and optimize CAWs. For simplicity, we refer to this henceforth as just "experiment".

ExtremeXP framework. Collection of tools that support users in conducting ExtremeXP experiments. For simplicity, we refer to this henceforth as just "framework".

User. The users of the framework are data analysts or domain experts with a vested interest in the development and operation of a CAW.

User intent. In the ExtremeXP framework, an intent is the main input for the end users to express their "intention" with the underlying data. Intents should primarily describe the analytical process (e.g., *prediction, visualization, simulation*) to be applied over the available datasets, together with user-defined constraints (e.g., *certain lower limit for accuracy*) and other (non-functional) user requirements (e.g., *resource availability to be taken into account*).

ExtremeXP opts for two types of user intents:

1. **Expressed user intents.** Such intents are explicitly provided by the end user in one of the two following formats:
 - a. **Structured intent.** In this case, the users use a form-like interface and via drop-down options (previously fed from the metadata knowledge base), construct the intent in a more structured and possibly more detailed manner. For instance:
 - Type of intent: *predict*

- Algorithm kind: *classification*
 - Algorithm: *Support Vector Machine*
 - Dataset: *manufacturing.csv*
 - Variable to predict: *failure*
 - Variables to consider: *f1, f2, f3, f4*
 - Constraint: *accuracy >= 90*
 - Non-functional requirements: *Minimize - CPU/GPU*
- b. **Textual intent.** In this case, the users use a chat-based interface and express their intent as text. For instance:
- *“I want to detect a manufacturing machine failure and its type (electrical or mechanical), knowing the positions of the machine table and the motor, as well as the intensity/current supplied to the motor. For that, I need an accuracy of at least 90%, and I have limited CPU/GPU resources available.”*
2. **Learned user intents.** Such intents are learned from previous experimentation and profiling of user interactions with the system. In this case, the system predicts user intents to proactively generate the desired CAWs and variability points and provide more personalized and smoother experience for the user. Users can at any time intervene and complete/modify the recommended intent.

Experiment specification. This includes:

- A description of the CAW itself. Such description includes the tasks to be performed and their data and control dependencies.
- Any *variability points* and *their domain*. A variability point is an aspect of the CAW that can be changed and can refer to (i) different task implementations (e.g., different ML algorithms), (ii) different task inputs (e.g., different datasets), (iii) different hyperparameters, (iv) different task/workflow deployments (e.g., on CPUs/GPUs). Each variability point has a domain that defines a set or range of its possible values.
- *Metrics* to be computed. A metric refers to a measurable property (i) of the whole CAW (e.g., end-to-end execution time), (ii) of a particular task (e.g., memory consumption of ML training), or (iii) of an output of a task (e.g., accuracy of produced ML model, user satisfaction level given a task’s outcome).
- Any *soft* and *hard constraints* related to the execution of the CAW. A hard constraint should never be violated (e.g., memory consumed below a certain limit), while a soft constraint is essentially an optimization objective (e.g., minimize memory consumption). A constraint can be defined with reference to e.g., a metric and/or deployment option.

2.1.1 Experiment dimensions and attributes

To fit the different needs of its use cases and of its future users beyond the project duration, ExtremeXP has a relatively broad view of an experiment. To delineate this view, ExtremeXP experiment is categorized along all five dimensions listed in Figure 1. Namely:

- **By experiment specification method.** Is the experiment specified fully by the user? Or is the experiment specification generated by an intent?
- **By experimentation goal.** Is the goal of the experiment to just run a single CAW or run and compare different variants of a CAW? In the latter case, are all the variants of the CAW supposed to be run and compared to each other or can variants be skipped (if, e.g., there is a high probability of being suboptimal)?
- **By user involvement.** Is the user involved in the process of selecting which CAW variants to run in an optimization experiment? If so, how often?

- **By context involvement.** Is an options explorer (e.g., ML model, Bayesian network, or Markov decision process trained/calibrated based on past experiments) consulted to suggest which CAW variants to run and which not?
- **By openness.** Can the CAW be changed (in predefined points in the experiment process) or not while an experiment is running?

Figure 1: Different experiment dimensions (green) and attributes (blue) considered in ExtremeXP.

Given the above dimensions, to fully classify an experiment, we need to specify its property for each of the five dimensions. We can, for instance, talk about an *intent-based, full-exploration, fully-automated, non-context-driven, closed* experiment as well as about a *fully-specified, optimization, partially automated, context driven, open* one.

The 12 identified experiment attributes are described in detail in Table 1.

Table 1 Description of the experiment attributes

Dimension	Attribute	ID	Description
Experiment specification method	Fully-specified	1	The user provides a full specification of the experiment to be run that includes the description of the CAW, the metrics to be computed, any variability points and their domain, and any soft and hard constraints related to the execution of the CAW. The specification needs to follow the ExtremeXP meta-model described in Section 3. The specification is transformed into one or more CAW variants (in a CAW variant, all variability points are set to a concrete value), which are executed on the framework. While specifying the experiments, users can start from scratch or select and customize pre-existing sub-workflows (corresponding to steps in a CAW) modeling common CAW tasks such as data discovery, data integration, data augmentation, and model selection. Such nodes are packaged within the “ExtremeXP CAW repository” developed within WP3.
	Intent-based	2	The user provides a natural language prompt to the framework (e.g., “find a classifier with at least 90% accuracy on this test dataset”). An experiment specification is fully generated in an automated way. Then, as in fully-specified experiments, the

			specification is transformed into one or more CAW variants that are executed in the framework. When specifying intents, users can also have access to the ExtremeXP CAW repository described in the “fully-specified” experiment case.
Experimentation goal	Single-shot	3	The framework receives an experiment specification (generated or not) that has no variability points. As a result, the specification is transformed into a single experiment which is executed on the framework. The metrics specified in the experiment are collected and presented to the user. When there is probability in the run of the CAW, it can be executed several times so that statistics over its metrics are calculated. This experiment property is chosen when the user is interested in simply benchmarking their CAW in a systematic way.
	Full-exploration	4	The framework receives an experiment specification (generated or not) with variability points. The framework transforms this specification into <i>all the possible CAW variants</i> by taking the cartesian product over all the possible values of all variability points. These variants are executed (in a sequence or in parallel) and the specified metrics are collected and presented in a comparative fashion to the user. This experiment property is chosen for sensitivity analysis, i.e., when the user needs to get a descriptive overview of the impact of the different variability points in their CAW.
	Optimization	5	As in a full-exploration experiment, the framework receives an experiment specification (generated or not) with variability points and transforms it into CAW variants. However, instead of scheduling the execution of all of them (as in the full-exploration case), the framework schedules the execution of variants in iterations. At each iteration, only a subset (even a single one) of the variants is executed. The execution results (metrics, outputs) are used to inform the decision of which variants to execute in the next iteration, together with the <i>hard and soft constraints</i> of the experiment. Metrics of only the executed variants – <i>a subset of all the possible ones</i> – are collected and presented, with an emphasis on the best-performing variants (the “optimal” ones). Optimality is determined based on the soft constraints present in the experiment specification. This experiment property is chosen to find the best-performing CAW variant in an efficient way, i.e., without having to run all possible variants as in a full-exploration experiment.
User involvement	User-driven	6	The framework receives an experiment specification (generated or not) and transforms it into CAW variants. When asked, the user decides which variant(s) to execute and in which order. To achieve this, the ExtremeXP framework provides several standardized interfaces for (i) showing relevant experiment results and metrics to the user, and (ii) collecting user input. This experiment property provides full control to the user and can help streamline an experimentation process performed by an expert user.

	Fully-automated	7	The framework receives an experiment specification (generated or not) and transforms it into CAW variants. Contrary to the user-driven property, the framework itself decides which variant(s) to execute and with which order. To do so, the framework uses an optimization/search algorithm such as a genetic algorithm, gradient descent, or multi-armed bandit to find the most promising candidate for execution in an automated way, i.e., without involving the user. This experiment property is similar to AutoML processes that typically take the user out of the optimization loop.
	Partially-automated	8	The framework receives an experiment specification (generated or not) and transforms it into CAW variants. Being a combination of user-driven and fully-automated properties, the framework <i>involves the user in some of the decisions</i> on which variants to run and in which order but also uses a search/optimization algorithm to <i>take the rest of the decisions in an automated way</i> . This experiment property is a compromise between full user control and full automation and can be used by users with some expertise in CAW optimization. Such a combination is a novel and important feature of our proposed framework.
Context involvement	Context-driven	9	The framework receives an experiment specification (generated or not) and transforms it into CAW variants. In this case, the user and/or the optimization/search algorithm taking decisions on which CAW variants to run and with which order are supported by an <i>option explorer</i> . The option explorer is based on knowledge generated by the <i>analysis of past experiments</i> and can take the form of, e.g., event-condition-action rules, trained classifier, Bayesian network, or a Markov decision process. It helps increase the efficiency of running an experiment by narrowing down its variability space. Note that an option explorer can be used with and without a user in the loop. This experiment property harnesses the power of past experiments in streamlining the execution of new experiments, a powerful feature of our proposed framework.
	Non-context-driven	10	When an experiment does not contain an option explorer to support the user or the optimization/search algorithm in taking decisions on which CAW variants to run and in which order (see context-driven case), it is simply a non-context-driven experiment.
Openness	Open	11	Given this experiment property, the CAW can be changed while an experiment is running, in predefined points in the experiment process. For example, extra steps with their variability points may be added to the CAW, or steps may be removed. This reflects the situation when the experiment developer decides to pause the experiment and adjust/reimplement its workflow.
	Closed	12	Given this experiment property, the CAW of an experiment cannot be changed after the experiment execution has started. This does not mean that the workflow is not dynamic. This means all decision points (e.g., prompts to the user) and the control is already embedded in the workflow, and that the workflow code does not change while the experiment is running.

2.2 Illustration of main concepts on a use case

This section illustrates the key ExtremeXP concepts and abstractions introduced in Section 2.1 on one of the ExtremeXP use cases, UC4, supported by MOBY (an ExtremeXP partner). MOBY is a transportation software company that specializes in digital transportation surveys. It has built a mobile application, MobyApp, that can be used by participants of such surveys in order to easily record different characteristics of their trips during the duration of a survey (e.g. 1 month). A MobyApp user essentially allows several mobile phone sensor data (GPS, accelerometer, etc.) to be recorded while using the app and streamed to the MOBY servers. There, data analytics workflows identify, for each data stream, the beginning and end (in terms of time and position) of “trips”, as well as other metadata for each trip useful to transportation planners. Of importance is the mode of transportation used in each trip, as well as the reason behind performing the trip. The data analytics workflows of MOBY attempt to automatically derive those from the data streams, using the labels provided by MobyApp users as ground truth.

The above MOBY case can be described using ExtremeXP concepts in the following way:

Complex analytics workflow (CAW). The CAW is the data collection and analytics workflow operated by MOBY. It is used to determine and characterize, based on training ML models with mobile phone sensor data from their end-users (e.g., users of the MOBY App), the trips of their end-users, including aspects like trip start and stop times and positions, modes of transport (car, bus, bicycle, etc.) and reason for traveling (going home, work, etc.).

ExtremeXP experiment. Optimizing the CAW of MOBY by choosing the best *ML trip mode classifier*, i.e., the one with the best combination of accuracy and training time. The classifier predicts the transportation mode for each trip (foot, bike, bus, car, etc.). According to the experiment classification scheme, we can define it as an *intent-based, optimization, fully automated, non-context-driven, closed experiment*.

User. The data scientist or transportation engineer of MOBY responsible for operating the CAW in the most effective and efficient way.

Intent. A possible formulation of intent is “find a classifier with min 80% accuracy to predict the transportation mode for each trip given mobile sensor data”.

Figure 2: UC4 workflow - MOBY case.

Experiment specification.

- *Description of the CAW itself.* There are in total 4 tasks in a sequential dependency with each other in this CAW, as depicted in Figure 2.
- *Metrics to be computed.* Accuracy and training time of the ML classifier outputted by task 3.
- *Variability points and their domain.* One variability point, ML algorithm, with 2 values, Decision Tree and Naive Bayes.
- *Related soft and hard constraints.* The soft constraint is that the accuracy of the ML classifier outputted by task 3 should be maximized and the hard constraint that the training time (on the infrastructure chosen MOBY) cannot exceed 30 mins.

ExtremeXP framework. The framework is not dependent on this MOBY case but is designed to accommodate different experiments performed both by MOBY and by the other four use case

partners of ExtremeXP. As such, ExtremeXP covers a broad spectrum of diverse CAWs and related experiments.

The way the framework is designed to accommodate the needs of the different experiments and use case partners is described next.

2.3 Framework

The ExtremeXP framework is a collection of interacting software components and related databases and repositories provided by the ExtremeXP partners. Each ExtremeXP use case partner provides several experiments to run in the framework; for each experiment, depending on the attributes featured by it (Section 2.1), different parts of the framework are used or activated.

From a high-level perspective, the framework consists of four modules, FM1-FM4 (Figure 3). Each module contains several software components, databases, and repositories. More details of the architecture of the framework, including the internal architecture of each module, are provided in Section 6. Here we describe the overall functionality and responsibilities of each module to illustrate how the five experiment dimensions corresponding to a total of 12 experiment attributes (Figure 1) are supported by the framework.

FM1 – Experiment Modelling. This module provides the entry point for the users of the framework, i.e., for the data engineers who gather the requirements from domain experts and are responsible for specifying experiments. To support both “fully-generated” and “intent-based” experiments, Experiment Modelling includes both editors for specifying experiments explicitly (by prescribing the Complex Analytics Workflow - CAW, metrics, variability points, and constraints), and for specifying intents which are used for generating experiments in a semi-automated way. Moreover, while modelling experiments, data engineers may choose to select predefined analytic tasks (corresponding, e.g., to common tasks such as data discovery and integration, and model or feature selection) from a library, configure them, and add them to their experiment specifications (i.e., models). This may save them time from specifying such common tasks every time from scratch. Research performed primarily in WP3 and WP4 of ExtremeXP is expected to populate such a library with several configurable analytic tasks. In the end, the result of experiment modelling is a number of experiment models that specify all the essential aspects of an experiment. The meta-model for specifying all these aspects is described in detail in Section 3.

Figure 3: ExtremeXP Framework Modules (FMs).

FM2 – Experiment Execution. This module gets the experiment specification and executes it. The module implements several execution strategies that correspond to “single-shot”, “full-exploration”, and “optimization” experiments. The execution strategy for single-shot experiments, for instance, simply runs a single CAW (since there are no variants) and saves its results in the databases. For full-exploration experiments, it performs a factorial design over all the variability points present in the experiment specification, resulting in several CAW variants that are run either sequentially or in parallel. Finally, for optimization experiments, the module hosts different optimization algorithms that can be used for providing the next CAW variant to run. In any case, “running a CAW variant” means performing its tasks in the order prescribed in the CAW. Such tasks may involve interacting with the Knowledge Management module to load or save datasets (inputs/outputs of tasks in the CAW). Finally, to support context-driven experiments (Section 2.1.1), Experiment Execution contains an Options Explorer that is built from past experiment executions and is able to predict which CAW variants are more promising to run (hence limiting the variability space of an experiment and speeding up its overall execution). The foundations behind such an Options Explorer are described in Section 4.

FM3 – User Interaction. This module is responsible for keeping the human in the loop in the execution of experiments. From one side, it is responsible for retrieving data from the Databases that are used for creating visualizations and explanations for both data engineers and domain experts. These are important for guiding experts making choices (e.g. aiding dataset selection) in user-driven experiments. From the other side, it acts as the frontend via which users interact with the framework during the execution of experiments. Until now, we foresee two such interactions: (1) data engineers controlling the lifecycle of experiments, e.g. being able to stop/pause them or change the execution

plan of an experiment; (2) domain experts evaluating the results of CAW variants and providing so-called “user metrics”, i.e. metrics such as “user acceptance” or “satisfaction level” that characterize the fit-for-purposeness of the result. This is an important module for the framework since, via the different levels of user interaction that is provided, both “user-driven”, “fully-automated”, and “partially-automated” experiments are supported. Finally, we envision that User Interaction will eventually also allow data engineers to change the underlying CAW of experiments on-the-fly via a sophisticated interface – this way also “open” experiments could be supported.

FM4 – Knowledge Management. This module is responsible for saving and retrieving data pertaining to the execution of experiments and for providing secure access to the datasets used or produced by the experiments. The data that are saved refer to the specification of running or already run experiments, calculated metrics for each experiment but also for each CAW variant within an experiment, metadata pertaining to the execution and the progress of experiments (e.g., duration), as well as metadata pertaining to the outputs of CAW variants (e.g., the location of the produced datasets). Datasets are provided by data creators and are made available via a distributed file system. Data engineers are responsible for specifying data access policies, which are hosted by Knowledge Management. Experiment Modelling, Experiment Execution and User Interaction modules must go through the Knowledge Management module whenever they need to obtain access to datasets. This module supports framework-wide trustworthiness and traceability, as explained in more detail in Section 5.

3 Meta-model

In this section we provide the meta-model of the experiment workflows. The definitions of our workflows are heavily inspired by BPMN [1]. The exact relation is described in Section 3.12.1.

Contrary to the existing workflow languages (such as BPMN), the meta-model we have developed in ExtremeXP brings in several important innovations which directly support the key innovations targeted by the ExtremeXP project. The key novelties are:

- Support for reusability of workflows – to allow users to be able to build experiments out of existing higher level building blocks (in the form of reusable workflows).
- Support for parameterization of workflows – to allow for exploratory and optimization experiments which traverse the parameter space of a workflow.
- Support definition and collection of performance metrics – to allow for optimization experiments and also for meta-analysis over past experiments.
- Support for human-in-the loop and UI integration – to enable experiments which integrate and take advantage of user feedback during the experiment.

As a particular concrete syntax of the meta-model instances in this section, we use a graphical notation explained along the individual elements of the meta-model. For examples of the meta-model instances, we use the workflow defined in Section 2.2.

We use the terms “model” and “meta-model” as they have been defined by OMG in [2]. The model “is information selectively representing some aspect of a system based on a specific set of concerns”, and the meta-model describes what can be used in a model. The meta-model describes the basic concepts of the workflow and the relationships of the concepts. In the text that accompanies the respective parts of the meta-model, we further explain the semantics of the concepts.

For the visualization of the meta-model itself, we use a subset of UML class diagrams. For better readability of the text, we omit the “meta” prefix when describing the meta-model elements (i.e., meta-class is referred to as a class, meta-attribute as an attribute, etc.).

In addition to having the ability to describe a workflow, the meta-model further connects this to visualization and analytics. Furthermore, the meta-model supports the design of workflows by allowing the designer to compose the workflow in a top-down or bottom-up manner. This is realized by providing hierarchical composition over workflows and giving the possibility to reuse and customize sub-workflows.

3.1 Meta-model structure

As shown in Figure 4, the meta-model is organized into eight packages. This allows for easy extensibility. The packages are as follows:

- **Data package** – describes data properties like ownership, governance, data quality, data trustworthiness, data origin, etc.
- **Workflow package** – describes workflows (individual steps, forks, etc.).
- **Deployment package** – describes a configuration of workflow steps for execution (in other words, deployment of a workflow).
- **ExperimentSpace package** – describes which experiments should be performed and which particular values of parameters should be used.
- **UserIntent package** – describes user preferences and intent.
- **Analysis package** – describes “what to measure and how”.
- **UI package** – describes a user interface that can be attached to tasks/groups in a workflow.
- **SecurityContext package** – describes security for users and data.

3.2.1 Workflow

Figure 6 The Workflow, Node, and Task classes

The Workflows class (see Figure 6) represents a whole workflow. It is composed of multiple Nodes and Links that interconnect the Nodes. Invariably, the workflow needs to have at least a single node.

The Workflow extends the Task class (Section 3.2.4), meaning that a complex task in a workflow can be modelled as a sub-workflow.

The Workflow has no particular graphical notation as it is expressed by the tasks, links, etc. with their own graphical notation.

3.2.2 Node

The Node class (see Figure 6) is abstract and represents a common parent for “actions” in a workflow.

3.2.3 Event

The Event class (see Figure 6) is a special kind of a workflow node. There are two possible events – the START of a workflow and the END of a workflow.

The graphical notation is described in Table 2 (see Figure 12 for an example).

Table 2 Graphical notation for Event

START	
END	

The Task class (see Figure 7) represents an individual task in a workflow. It extends the Node class. It can have multiple data inputs and outputs and multiple parameters.

The Task is either a simple one that is defined by its description (assuming to point to the actual implementation of the task) or a complex one that is defined as a sub-workflow (through the containment on Workflow). Also, the Task can be modeled as an abstract one, i.e., without an actual “implementation”, which is later specified in the Deployment (see Section 3.6).

The `InputData` and `OutputData` are named, but they are not further modeled, i.e., they are considered unstructured blocks. The `InputData` is further divided into `ExternalInputData` and `IntermediateInputData` to distinguish between data that comes to the workflow from the environment and input data that are internally generated within the workflow by another task (as the `OutputData` – thus, there is the association to the particular `OutputData`).

As the name suggests, the parameters are used for parametrizations of the Tasks. There are two kinds of parameters – static ones and dynamic ones.

The `StaticParameter` is defined by its name, type, and value (the value can be set for different experiments in the `DesignSpace` – see Section 3.7). On the other hand, the `DynamicParameter` specifies its value to be obtained from the `OutputData` (that is produced by another Task).

Additionally, the Task may compute a number of Metrics as a part of its execution. These typically represent some summary statistics that characterize a dataset that Task operates on or has produced (e.g., the accuracy of a created ML model) or that characterize the execution of the task itself (e.g., its throughput or performance). The metric is typically a result of some computation represented by the class `Algorithm` from the `UserIntent` package (Section 3.8). The association of the Metric to the Algorithm is meant to support suggestions on workflow tasks based on user intents (as planned in WP4).

Data (no visual distinction between input/output data and external/intermediate)	
Outputting/Inputting data	
Parameter	

3.2.5 Operator

The Operator class (see Figure 8) represents forks and joins in a workflow. It is an abstract class and there are four possible forking operators and four corresponding join operators. The fork operators are as follows:

- Parallel operator – creates parallel paths of execution in a workflow. All the paths are executed potentially simultaneously.
- Exclusive operator – creates alternative paths of execution in a workflow. Only a single path is executed.
- Inclusive operator – creates alternative but possibly parallel paths in a workflow. It represents a combination of the Parallel and Exclusive operators; while the Parallel operator executes all the paths and the Exclusive executes a single path, here several paths can be chosen (based on the conditions) and executed in parallel.
- Complex operator – is similar to the Inclusive operator but allows specifications of complex conditions. For example, consider a fork with four possible paths to continue, and we want to enable the execution of the second one only if the first one is also selected or similarly, the fourth one is allowed only if the third one is enabled (i.e., the paths are mutually excluded in pairs).

The join operators just follow the fork operators.

Figure 8 The Operator class

The graphical notation is described in Table 4.

Table 4 Graphical notation for Operators

Parallel operator	
Exclusive operator	
Inclusive operator	
Complex operator	

3.2.6 Link

The Link class (Figure 9) represents links between nodes (Task, Event, or Operator). A link is an oriented connection between strictly two nodes – one is an input node, and another is an output node. The Link is an abstract class with three particular subclasses. They are as follows:

- RegularLink – is a regular, unconditional flow from one node in a workflow to another one.

- ConditionalLink – is a flow that is executed when an associated condition is satisfied. There must be multiple links from a particular node so that another flow can be selected when the condition is not satisfied.
- ExceptionalLink – is a flow that is taken when an exception occurs in a node execution. It is similar to the ConditionalLink, but the ExceptionalLink emphasizes that it is a handling of an exception.

Figure 9 The Link class

The graphical notation is described in Table 5.

Table 5 Graphical notation for Links

RegularLink	
ConditionalLink	
ExceptionalLink	

Remark: A conditional flow can be modelled either with the ConditionalLinks or with the Exclusive operator – from this point of view, the ConditionalLink is redundant. Nevertheless, its inclusion can significantly simplify the workflows.

3.2.7 ParameterType

Figure 10 The DataType class

The ParameterType class (see Figure 10) defines a type used for Parameters. It is an abstract class with three concrete subclasses representing a particular kind of type. These are (i) primitive types, (ii) arrays of a particular type, and (iii) structures. The Primitives are either numbers, Booleans (true, false), Strings, or unstructured binary large objects (BLOBs). Arrays and Structures have the traditional semantics.

3.2.8 Group

Figure 11 Group and UI

The Group class (see Figure 11) allows for horizontally grouping tasks. Similarly, like in the case of the Task, the group can have attached MetaData. This is meant for situations when a set of tasks is supposed to be annotated by metadata, but these tasks do not directly form a sub-workflow. An example is, for instance, grouping all tasks performed by a particular user.

Groups can naturally overlap. The graphical notation is described in Table 6.

Table 6 Graphical notation for Group

Group	
-------	--

3.2.9 UI

The *UI* class (see Figure 11) allows for attaching a user interface to a Task (and thus also to a workflow as the Workflow is a subclass of the Task class) and groups. The *UI* is abstract, and its particular realizations are defined in the UI package (see Section 3.10).

The driving motivation here is to allow user interaction in some steps of the workflow. The tasks with user interaction have an instance of the UI class attached to provide a place where the user interface and the interaction with a user can be specified. The graphical notation is described in Table 7.

Table 7 Graphical notation for UI

UI attached to a group	
UI attached to a task	
Icons representing UI variants (mobile, desktop, web, modular)	

3.3 Metadata

The Metadata class (see Figure 11) models arbitrary additional information as a key-value pair. Thus, each piece of metadata has a name and a value. The name is hierarchical. The MetaData can be attached to Tasks or Groups of tasks. Also, it is employed in the Data package (see Section 3.5).

3.4 Running example modeling

Figure 12 shows the running example modeled using the meta-model. The above-described notation is used. The group (with the name “*user performed*”) is applied to highlight the “manual” nature of the grouped tasks.

The “Mode detection classifier training” and “Activity detection classifier training” are tasks modeled as subflows (note the plus in the rectangle). We do not include their visualization here as they are just linear flows.

Due to the readability of the figure, the data and their flow are sketched only.

Figure 12 The Running example

3.5 Data package

The Data package (see Figure 13) primarily describes the DataSet, which, as the name suggests, holds data sets that are an input of a workflow or that are generated (i.e., output) by a workflow. From the point of view of the meta-model, the DataSet is not further structured. The DataSet in the meta-model corresponds to the actual dataset which is managed by the components in the Knowledge Management module of the reference architecture (see Section 6.3.4) – namely the Dataset Catalog and the Distributed File System Management.

Figure 13 Data package

The package further defines the ComputedMetric class, which is a specialization of MetaData and which is used in the Deployment package (see Section 3.6). The ComputedMetric corresponds to a metric that has been computed by a task and stored in the Metrics Management component in the reference architecture (see Section 3.6). By generalizing the metric as the Metadata, we allow this computed metric to be attached to a dataset or to a task. This allows us to collect data meta-data like performance, resource consumption, accuracy, etc.

3.6 Deployment package

The DeployedWorkflow (Figure 14) defines a *deployment plan* of a workflow, i.e., an actual configuration of a workflow. The Workflow class may declare parameters or abstract tasks, which facilitate the workflow reuse and composition. The DeployedWorkflow specifies all the free variables and forms a fully specified workflow that is ready to be executed by the Executionware (see Section 6.3.2). Thus, the deployed workflow is the concept that directly realizes the single-shot experiment (see Section 2.1.1).

As described in Section 3.2.4, a Task can be an abstract one (its attribute *isAbstract* set to true). The DeployedWorkflow determines a particular Workflow and maps the abstract tasks to particular workflows using the ConfiguredTasks association. The ConfiguredTask refers to the target Task (i.e., the one to be configured) and to the Task that is used as the replacement for the target task.

The ConfiguredTask may be used to specify configuration of not only abstract tasks, but also regular ones. In this case, this provides a mechanism for customization of existing workflows by replacing some existing tasks with their alternatives. This addresses the situations when, for instance, another predictor is to be used in an existing workflow.

Figure 14 The Configuration package

Remark on task compatibility for configurations: A task can be configured only with a task that (i) is not abstract and (ii) has the same inputs and outputs. I.e., the *type* of a task (the term *type* here has the same meaning as *type* in programming languages) is defined by its inputs and outputs, and tasks have structural compatibility.

In addition to the ConfiguredTask, the DeployedWorkflow specifies assignments between DataSets and InputData resp. OutputData. The InputDataSetAssignment provides the assignment of a DataSet to ExternalInputData (i.e., the data that comes to the workflow execution from outside). Similarly, the OutputDataSetAssignment assigns an OutputData (produced by a task) to a resulting DataSet. Plus, the OutputDataSetAssignment also assigns the Metric (that is to be computed by the Task) with the actual computed metric.

Remark on concrete syntax: We intentionally do not provide a graphical notation for capturing configurations. This would be too cumbersome to depict graphically. We consider textual notation a far superior alternative. This notation will be developed along with the whole domain-specific language (DSL) in year 2 of the project.

3.7 ExperimentSpace package

The ExperimentSpace (Figure 15) is the meta-model concept that directly supports the full-exploration and optimization experiments (see Section 2.1.1). It defines which deployment plans have to be executed (in DeployedWorkflowExperimentSpace) and which actual values of tasks' parameters should be used. The ParameterDomain specifies these values.

The ExperimentSpaceConstraint defines a predicate over the possible values, telling whether these values are valid; thus, the DeployedWorkflow can be executed with the values. The predicate itself is expected to be a Boolean expression in a given programming language (e.g., Python or R) that is understood by the Experimentation Engine (see Section 6.3.2).

Figure 15 The ExperimentSpace package

3.8 UserIntent package

As the name suggests, the UserIntent package (Figure 16) describes the user's intent and overall workflow objective. The UserIntent package provides the skeletons for basic concepts in order to align these concepts with the workflow. These concepts are planned to be further elaborated in WP4, where the work on user intents capturing/anticipating and generating workflows based on those user intent is planned.

The core element here is the Intent, which is satisfied by an Algorithm that can be implemented by a Task in a Workflow. Depending on an Algorithm implementation, a specific HyperParameter can be specified to parametrize the corresponding task. Intent is further expressed in more details through the WorkflowObjective, which can be parametrized by multiple Constraints. The HardConstraint are those that must always be satisfied and are specified through the expression (e.g., "Keep the memory consumption during the workflow execution under 60%" or "Solve the intent using Random Forest algorithm"), while the SoftConstraint is essentially an optimization objective, specifying a set of Methods to be evaluated using corresponding workflow metrics (e.g., "Minimize the workflow execution time").

Lastly, to facilitate further learning and anticipating of user Intents and workflows, additional details about user and workflow characteristics are further modelled using the corresponding classes, UserCharacteristics and WorkflowCharacteristics, respectively.

Figure 16 UserIntent package

3.9 Analysis package

The Analysis package (see Figure 17) provides the skeletons of basic concepts related to analysis (developed in WP3).

Figure 17 Analysis package

Figure 18 ML model

The elaboration on these concepts is to be performed within WP3 deliverables. The classes depicted here are meant to provide the first alignment of the analysis with the workflows and experiments.

The key concept here is the ExecutedWorkflow, which represents a workflow that had been executed. As such, it points to the DeployedWorkflow and associates it with the User that has executed it and the UserFeedback that was collected. The metrics that are collected during the experiment are already captured by the Deployment package (though they are relevant to analysis).

The ExecutedWorkflow can be associated with several different types of Metadata. The one explicitly defined at this time is the MLModelMetadata that, as the name suggests, describes an ML model used in the workflows.

The ML Model structure is shown in Figure 18. It has been adopted from [3], where a detailed complete description can be found. In short, the ML Model presents a detailed metamodel for representing machine learning model metadata, featuring classes such as Configuration, Prediction, DataSet, Metric. This metamodel enables precise characterization and categorization of various aspects of machine learning models. The MLModel class encapsulates the overall model information, including its version, tasks, and script files. The Algorithm class categorizes the algorithm type, subdividing into traditional algorithms like SVM or decision trees, and advanced types like DNNs, with further specialization into CNNs, RNNs, etc. The Configuration class describes how the algorithm is parameterized for the particular task in terms of hyper parameters, use of datasets and mapping to HW and will bridge to the corresponding settings in the parameters ExtremeXP meta-model.

Another big area where WP3 relates to the workflow meta-model is by providing algorithms that compute certain metrics or analyze corresponding data. This is intended to be realized as a repository of reusable workflow patterns (e.g., an ML-training pattern for image classification, image data data-augmentation pattern). The “pattern” here corresponds to a (potentially abstract) sub-workflow (i.e., an instance of class Workflow). As such, it can be easily reused as a building block when designing new complex workflows. From the reference architecture perspective, these workflow patterns are stored in the Analytic Task Library (see Section 6.3.1).

3.10 UI package

Figure 19 UI package

The UI package (see Figure 19) allows for specifications of tasks’ user interfaces. The UI class (defined in the Workflow package, see Section 3.2) allows for attaching a user interface to a Task and/or Group. The UI class itself is abstract, and there are two particular realizations: the Blackbox UI and the Modular UI. The Blackbox, as the name suggests, is not further modeled, and either it can be a WebBased, DesktopBased, or MobileBased UI. On the other hand, the Modular UI is modelled in detail – see Figure 20.

Figure 20 Modular UI

A modular UI basically consists of a hierarchy of views. Some views are composite, i.e., they may aggregate other views. In the meta model, Composite Views are either Decorational or Layout Managers. Decorational Views are windows, borders, panes, etc., while Layout Managers control the layout of their child views using various methods that must be specified as part of such views. Composite Views may consist of a combination of other Composite Views and Content Views.

A Content View visualizes one or more instances of a whole or parts of a concept model. In the meta-model, the class Concept Model Fragment is a placeholder for a model describing the (parts of) the concept model that will be presented by the Content View. To determine which instances are to be presented by the Content View, it must be specified which concept (class, entity, etc.) in the concept model is the root or anchor. Given one instance of the concept model anchor, the information to be visualized is usually an instance hierarchy, with the anchor instance being the root of the instance hierarchy.

The meta-model also allows for specifying several UI Styles and Platform/modalities to be used in the visualization. Example UI Styles are map-based, graph-based, dashboard, form-based, list-based, and multimedia. Example Platform/modalities are PC with mouse/keyboard, mobile device with touch, augmented reality, audio interaction, and tabletop.

3.11 SecurityContext package

Currently, the package is empty, and its content will be defined by T2.3 in future deliverables.

3.12 Relation to existing workflow modeling approaches

3.12.1 Relation to BPMN (Business Process Model and Notation)

As already stated, the definitions of our workflows are heavily inspired by BPMN [1]. However, the inspiration is rather on the “pragmatic” side, i.e., we use almost the same top-level concepts (tasks, events, links, etc.); nevertheless, the corresponding meta-model is simplified to directly suit our needs as BPMN targets business workflows while we need to target analytics ones. Also, the graphical notation is almost one-to-one taken from BPMN. In the rest of this section, we provide a more detailed comparison between BPMN and our meta-model.

BPMN is a graphical representation of business processes and workflows. Its specification is maintained by OMG. Initially, it was only a graphical representation, but since version 2, it has also specified an XML format and can be directly executed by a BPMN engine (there are a number of both proprietary and open-source BPMN engines).

Compared to BPMN, we use the same following elements:

- Task has the same meaning as in BPMN. A simplification on our side is that in BPMN, the Task is always an atomic one, and there is a generic element Activity that can be either an atomic Task or a composed workflow. We model both atomic and composed workflows by the Task. The Parameters, Metadata, UI and Metrics are specific to our model and are included based on the project partners’ requirements.
- Data objects (InputData and OutputData) have the same meaning as in BPMN but are modeled differently, again based on the project partners’ requirements.
- Event has the same meaning as in BPMN. Compared to it, we need only two kinds of events – START and STOP – while BPMN also has an intermediate event (for synchronizations) that we do not need.
- Operator has the same meaning as in BPMN – however, in BPMN, it is called the Gateway. We chose a different name to align it more with analytics workflows. The kinds of operators (Exclusive, Parallel, etc.) are again taken from BPMN.

- Link has the same meaning as in BPMN – however, in BPMN, it is called Flow. We chose the Link name to not confuse it with a complete workflow. The kinds of links are again taken from BPMN; only we limited them to the kinds we need (regular, conditional, and exceptional).
- Group has the same meaning as in BPMN.

On the other hand, BPMN does not provide support for configurations and experimentations etc. (i.e., all other packages than Workflows) as BPMN targets a different primary purpose, and these are irrelevant for BPMN.

4 Probabilistic Options Explorer

4.1 Probabilistic model of data analytics

Probabilistic decision models are frameworks that incorporate uncertainty into decision-making processes by considering various possible outcomes and their probabilities. They emerged as a response to the recognition that real-world scenarios often involve unknowns, variability, and randomness. These models evolved to make more informed and optimal decisions in the face of uncertainty, leveraging probability theory to quantify uncertainties and their potential impact on outcomes. Probabilistic models play a fundamental role in data analytics, offering invaluable insights by accounting for uncertainty in data. Among these models, Markov Decision Processes (MDPs) and Bayesian networks stand out as powerful tools. MDPs are dynamic models used in decision-making processes under uncertainty. They're characterized by sequential decision-making where the outcome at each step depends only on the current state and the action taken, assuming a Markov property. MDPs enables systems to make optimal decisions in uncertain environments by maximizing expected rewards. On the other hand, Bayesian networks (BN) are graphical models representing probabilistic relationships among variables using directed acyclic graphs. These networks encode conditional dependencies between variables through probability distributions, allowing for efficient inference and reasoning under uncertainty. They excel in handling complex domains by capturing causal relationships and updating beliefs based on new evidence using Bayes' theorem. Unlike MDPs, Bayesian networks are static models. They excel in probabilistic reasoning, aiding in making informed decisions by incorporating prior knowledge and updating beliefs as new information becomes available. While MDPs focus on sequential decision-making, Bayesian networks emphasize probabilistic inference and causal relationships within a system. Both models play pivotal roles in data analytics, albeit in distinct domains and with differing emphases on temporal dynamics and causal dependencies.

In the context of ExtremeXP, the probabilistic model for data analysis and visualisation, puts the end user at the centre of complex processes (i.e., processes that involve and combine ML, data analysis, and simulation components) and corresponding visualizations. It considers that the end user is a domain expert (e.g., first respondent in disasters situations, transportation planner, maintainer of industrial plant or similar) that does not necessarily possess advanced technical skills (e.g., data management, machine learning, resource management or data querying languages), but is interested in the outcome of the complex analytics. The concept combines the two probabilistic methods at different stages, the MDP for delivering probabilistic decisions and recommending best performing datasets, algorithms, and deployment option (i.e. computing resources) for the algorithms on each individual stage; and BN that will use its prior knowledge to select an optimal for the user process flow for the data analytics. MDP and BN are increasingly used in different scientific fields for probabilistic modelling where directed and un-directed dependencies between variables exist, as important tools in decision-making process.

The initial concept of the probabilistic decision-making utilisation is composed of nine consecutive steps (Figure 21): (1) the user selects the domain of the data analysis (e.g. healthcare, preventing disasters and etc.) and describes his/her intent by using one of the suggested keywords or phrases (e.g. 'visualization', 'analysis of effect', 'prediction model', 'feature extraction', etc.). Moreover, the user defines the quality and quantity requirements related to the process-flow, in terms of hard constraints (e.g. number of dependent and independent relevant variables for the methods or algorithms, which are directly connected to the intent, geographical location for the deployment option selection and etc.) that have to be fully abide at all times and soft constraints (e.g. vCPU, vRAM, expected throughput, etc.) that are recommended to be abided as much as possible; (2) based on the selected hard constraints and context, the model is reduced to sub-models that are composed of states that satisfy the hard constraints; (3) unless the user uploads a personal dataset for the

experiment, the system will consider the soft constraints as input parameters for the MDP and an optimal dataset will be proposed; (4) based on the chosen dataset, its context and prior usage data, the BN will propose an optimal sub-model of methods (algorithms) that fit the already selected dataset; (5) by using the MDP, an optimal method (algorithm) is chosen out of the sub-model from the previous step; (6) based on the output from steps 4 and 5, a sub-model of potential deployment options is created; (7) using the output from the previous step and the soft constraints from step 1, the MDP determines an optimal deployment option for the algorithm; (8) the selected optimal options are proposed to the user for final approval of the experimental process-flow; (9) if the user approves and uses the proposed experiment process flow, at the end they are given the chance to express their rating on the proposed output, which will impact the reputation of the decision making process.

Figure 21 Outline of the baseline scenario

4.2 Probabilistic model specification

4.2.1 Bayesian network

In the context of ExtremeXP, we defined a vector $G=(D,M,O)$, where, D represents datasets, M represents methods that can be used in the experiment workflow and O represents deployment options, where the methods can be deployed and run, with countable set of values $\{d_1, d_2, \dots, d_b\}$, $\{m_1, m_2, \dots, m_c\}$, $\{o_1, o_2, \dots, o_d\}$, respectively. The set of possible methods corresponds to a given intent and satisfies the hard constraints for methods, while the set of possible deployment options satisfies the hard constraints for deployment.

We consider the initial set of model parameters that changes over time, with gaining more knowledge from experimenter's usage.

Initially, all choices of the datasets d_i , $1 \leq i \leq b$, are equally likely:

$$p_i = P(D = d_i) = \frac{1}{b}$$

Probabilities of choosing any method m_j , $1 \leq j \leq c$ for the chosen dataset d_i , $1 \leq i \leq b$, are initially equal to

$$q_{j|(D=d_i)} = P(M = m_j | D = d_i) = \frac{1}{c}$$

For the dataset d_i , $1 \leq i \leq b$, and the method m_j , $1 \leq j \leq c$, the conditional probability of choosing the deployment option o_k , $1 \leq k \leq d$

$$r_{k|(D=d_i, M=m_j)} = P(O = o_k | D = d_i, M = m_j) = \frac{1}{d}$$

In other words, at the beginning, all possible datasets, methods and deployment options are equally likely to be chosen and independent of each other, referring to the scenario with no previous knowledge or preference.

Overall, the model structure is represented in Figure 22.

Figure 22 Causal dependencies between datasets, methods and deployment options

A Bayesian network was built on the basis of the above-described dependencies between the datasets, methods and deployment options.

4.2.2 Markov decision process models

Dependencies between the datasets, between the methods and between the deployment options are described with three Markov decision processes. Let S_t be state variables with a finite state space $S = \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_N\}$ and A_t be decision variables with a finite action space $A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_N\}$ measured at time $t=0, 1, \dots$. The transition from state s to state s' at the step $t+1$ is made due to an action a with probability equal to:

$$p_{s,s'}^a = P(S_{t+1} = s' | S_t = s, A_t = a), \quad s, s' \in S$$

State transition probability matrix P_a defines transition probabilities from all states s to all successor states s' due to an action a .

MDP	State space s_1, s_2, \dots, s_N	Action	Initial $P_{s, s'}^a$
Datasets	d_1, d_2, \dots, d_b	Selection of a dataset	$\frac{1}{b}$
Methods	m_1, m_2, \dots, m_c	Selection of a method	$\frac{1}{c}$
Deployment	o_1, o_2, \dots, o_d	Selection of a deployment	$\frac{1}{d}$

Figure 23 General Markov decision process with description of the states, actions and initial probabilities of specific processes

Let $R_a(s, s')$ expected reward received after transitioning from state s to state s' , due to an action a . Further, let γ be a discount factor, which represents the difference in importance between current and future rewards, $0 \leq \gamma \leq 1$. Markov decision process is a tuple $M=(S, A, P_a, R_a, \gamma)$, where state transitions satisfy the Markov property. At the beginning, all initial probabilities are equal to

$$p_{s, s'}^a = P(S_1 = s' | S_0 = s) = \frac{1}{N}, s, s' \in S$$

The general structure of the Markov decision process is presented in Figure 23, together with the description of the states, actions and initial probabilities for Markov decision processes for datasets, methods and deployment.

4.3 Learning Bayesian network and Markov decision process

The conditional probabilities of the Bayesian network and transition probabilities of Markov decision process are changing over time by learning from the experimenter's usage. In the following text, we will describe how the information from the previously performed experiments is incorporated in the calculation of the probabilities.

4.3.1 Evolution of Bayesian network probabilities

Initial probabilities of the Bayesian network are evolving by collecting the information from the previously performed experiments. Let U_1, U_2, \dots, U_q denote users with the respective expertise scores E_1, E_2, \dots, E_q , where $0 \leq E_i \leq 1$. We propose the following measures for estimating the Bayesian network probabilities:

$$\hat{p}_i = \frac{1 + \sum_{l=1}^q E_l I_l(D = d_i)}{b + \sum_{l=1}^q E_l}, 1 \leq i \leq b,$$

$$\hat{q}_{j|(D=d_i)} = \frac{1 + \sum_{l=1}^q E_l I_l(M = m_j|D = d_i)}{c + \sum_{l=1}^q E_l}, 1 \leq j \leq c, 1 \leq i \leq b$$

$$\hat{r}_{k|(D=d_i, M=m_j)} = \frac{1 + \sum_{l=1}^q E_l I_l(O = o_k|D = d_i, M = m_j)}{d + \sum_{l=1}^q E_l},$$

$$1 \leq k \leq d, 1 \leq i \leq b, 1 \leq j \leq c$$

where $I_l(D=d_i)$ denotes the indicator that the l -th user chose the dataset d_i , $1 \leq i \leq b$, $I_l(M=m_j|D=d_i)$ indicator that they chose the method m_j , $1 \leq j \leq c$ given that $D=d_i$ and $I_l(O=o_k|D=d_i, M=m_j)$ denotes the indicator that the l -th user chose the deployment option o_k , $1 \leq k \leq d$, given that $D=d_i$ and $M=m_j$. Each count of the certain choice (value 1 of the indicator) is weighed with the user's expertise, giving the greater weight to the users with the higher expertise. Note that the probability estimates for methods are estimated for each chosen dataset, by calculating b probability estimates (first set is calculated for all users who selected dataset d_1 , then second set of probability estimates for all users who selected dataset d_2 , and so on). In the same manner, we calculate bc sets of probability estimates for deployment options, for each pair of values (d_i, m_j) .

4.3.2 Evolution of the MDP transition probabilities

In the same manner as with the BN probabilities, initial probabilities of the Markov decision process are evolving after gaining knowledge from the previous experiment workflows. The transition probability p_{s_i, s_j}^a , $1 \leq i, j \leq N$ is estimated from the data with:

$$\hat{p}_{s_i, s_j}^a = \frac{n_{i,j}}{\sum_{j=1}^N n_{i,j}}$$

where $n_{i,j}$ is the number of times transition from state s_i to s_j is made and $\sum_{j=1}^N n_{i,j}$ total number of all transitions from state s_i to N states.

4.4 Ranking of the options

4.4.1 Ranking of the Bayesian network paths

Probability associated with each path of the Bayesian network is calculated as

$$P(O = o_k|D = d_i, M = m_j)P(M = m_j|D = d_i)P(D = d_i), 1 \leq i \leq b, 1 \leq j \leq c, 1 \leq k \leq d$$

Paths are ranked by their probabilities and the path with the highest probability is offered to a new user as the best choice.

4.4.2 Utility function of Markov decision process

In MDPs the utility function, also known as the reward function or objective function, quantifies the desirability of the different states or state-action pairs within the environment. This function assigns a numerical value to each state or state-action pair, representing the immediate or long-term desirability or "utility" associated with being in that state or taking that action from that state. The goal in MDPs is typically to find a policy (a set of rules or actions) that maximizes the expected

cumulative utility or reward over time. In the context of ExtremeXP, the utility function quantifies the desirability of the available options based on the users' requirements. Essentially the Option Explorer will recommend to the users the options with highest utility value.

The algorithm for calculation of rewards inspects if the states of the model satisfy the constraints (depicted in step 1 of Figure 22). The more of the soft constraints are violated, the lower will be the reward assigned to the state, thus lower the utility of the given state. The utility function is calculated with the Bellman equation:

$$u(s) = \max_{a \in A} \sum_{s' \in S} p_{s,s'}^a (R_a(s, s') + \gamma u(s')) = r(s) + \gamma \max_{a \in A} \sum_{s' \in S} p_{s,s'}^a u(s')$$

where $r(s)$ is an immediate reward and $p_{s,s'}^a u(s')$ future discounted rewards. Utility function provides the ranking score for each state of Markov decision process. A detailed explanation of the algorithm for the calculation of rewards in MDP for deployment is presented in [4].

Value of the utility function is calculated by the iteration algorithm

$$\begin{aligned} u_1(s) &= r(s) \\ u_{i+1}(s) &= r(s) + \gamma \max_{a \in A} \sum_{s' \in S} p_{s,s'}^a u_i(s') \end{aligned}$$

where $u_1(s)$ is utility at the state s in the first-time step and $u_{i+1}(s)$ is the Bellman update (the maximum possible sum of discounted rewards at the step s in the $i+1$ time step).

5 Traceability and trustworthiness for experiment-driven analytics

In the context of experiment-driven analytics, ensuring trustworthiness and traceability is crucial. The concept of trustworthiness in data and analytics systems is rooted in three fundamental pillars: ability, integrity, and benevolence [5]. These pillars form the backbone of reliable and credible data processing and analytics environments.

Ability refers to the competence and capability of the data system to accurately and efficiently manage and process data. It encompasses the technical proficiency of the system in handling complex data sets, ensuring accurate analytics, and providing robust data management functionalities. Ability ensures that the system can meet the diverse and dynamic needs of users and applications.

Integrity relates to the honesty and accuracy of data processing and management. It involves ensuring that data is handled in a manner that is truthful, transparent, and free from corruption or unauthorized modification. Integrity in data systems means that users can trust the data and the outcomes of data analytics processes to be reliable and accurate.

Benevolence in the context of data systems refers to the good intentions and ethical considerations inherent in the management and use of data. It implies that the system is designed and operated with the best interests of users and stakeholders in mind, prioritizing data security, privacy, and ethical use of data.

5.1 Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC)

Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC) is a method of regulating access to objects (such as data and knowledge artifacts) based on attributes (characteristics) of users, the objects being accessed, and the environment in which the access request is made. ABAC is particularly suited for complex and dynamic environments where access needs can rapidly change and are highly contextual.

The ABAC model uses policies formed from attributes' logical combinations to grant access rights. These policies, requests, and responses are articulated in XACML, an OASIS standard [6]. A policy comprises rules that requesters must follow, implemented through algorithms at either the policy set (policy combining algorithms) or policy level (rule combining algorithms). These algorithms integrate various request evaluations to generate a single decision. Policies link to 'targets' like resources, action types, context expressions, or their mix, where a context expression specifies the conditions for access permission. Upon a request, the policy rules are assessed using attribute values to produce a decision-inclusive response.

ABAC systems can generate detailed logs and metadata about each access request and the decision-making process. This includes information about who requested access, what data was requested, under what conditions, and why access was granted or denied. This level of detail contributes to the integrity and transparency of the system.

By tracing and recording the attributes and circumstances of each access request, the ABAC mechanism contributes to data provenance - the ability to trace and verify the origin, movement, and history of data. This is crucial for understanding the data lifecycle, ensuring data integrity, and providing explainability for any data processing actions. This transparency reinforces the trust in the data system by making it possible to audit and understand how and why data was used or shared.

5.1.1 Data processing in Extreme XP framework

We are pivoting our efforts towards embedding granularity within the ExtremeXP framework. We are aiming to intricately control access to the input data files, the key functionality in the experimentation flows and new output files created within the framework.

Integrating detailed access control within the ExtremeXP framework represents a significant advancement in how data security and access management are conceptualized and executed. This proactive approach aligns with the project's goal of establishing a robust, secure, and adaptable data management environment.

The Extreme XP framework architecture introduces an approach to data processing, especially in the context of integrating human interests and responsibilities, creating explainable and auditable metadata. This subsection delves into the generic approach within the framework to ensure non-repudiation and foster transparency through explainable metadata.

5.1.1.1. Non-repudiation

Non-repudiation in data processing ensures that actions or decisions made by individuals (i.e., humans in the loop) can be unequivocally traced back to them. This accountability is critical in scenarios where decisions significantly impact the data processing outcomes. In the ExtremeXP framework, mechanisms are put in place to authenticate all interactions and decisions made by humans. This involves capturing digital signatures or other forms of verifiable credential evidence that link actions to specific individuals. These credentials are used as input in any interaction with the ABAC mechanism and framework.

5.1.1.2. Humans in the loop

Humans in the loop play a crucial role in supervising, guiding, or intervening in automated processes. Their decisions and inputs can significantly influence the outcomes of data processing. The framework ensures that the involvement of humans is transparent and accountable. It establishes clear guidelines and protocols for human intervention, ensuring that actions are justifiable and traceable.

5.1.1.3. Explainable Metadata

Explainable metadata involves documenting the data processing steps, decisions made, and the rationale behind these decisions in a comprehensible and transparent manner. This is crucial for understanding how and why specific data processing outcomes were achieved. In the Extreme XP framework, each step of data processing is accompanied by metadata that explains the processes, algorithms used, and the decision-making logic. This includes detailing the parameters, models, and any human inputs involved.

5.2 Threat model

Our threat model considers specific attacks that could compromise the security and trustworthiness of the ExtremeXP framework. These attacks are categorized based on their potential impact on the system's integrity, availability, confidentiality, and accountability.

5.2.1 Integrity threats

Integrity threats involve actions that compromise the accuracy, consistency, and trustworthiness of data and system operations. These threats can manifest through various forms of tampering, where attackers alter (modify, delete, or inject) false information into the system. The impact of such threats is significant, as they can lead to corrupted data, unreliable system outputs, and overall mistrust in the system's operations.

Data Source Poisoning attacks: An attacker alters the input data files with false information, corrupting the experiment.

Tampering of Results or Outputs: An attacker alters the results of the experiments, which could lead to incorrect intermediate or final experiment results.

Tampering with Logs: An attacker alters logs, affecting the historical accuracy and traceability of the log records.

Tampering with Metadata: An attacker alters the metadata repository to depreciate the value, usability, or trustworthiness of experiments, databases, or machine learning model.

5.2.2 Availability threats

Availability threats pertain to risks that can hinder or stop users from accessing the system or its resources as intended. These threats often target the reliability and continuous functionality of the system, making it unavailable or significantly degraded for legitimate users.

Single point of failure (SPOF) Attack: An attacker sends an excessive number of repetitive requests to the access control to stop the whole system from functioning. A Single Point of Failure (SPOF) attack exploits the centralized nature of the access control system, which compromises the decision point that manages access control policies.

5.2.3 Attacks on Confidentiality threats

Confidentiality threats encompass risks that lead to unauthorized disclosure of sensitive information. These threats can arise from various sources, including cyber-attacks that exploit vulnerabilities in the system to access confidential data. The impact of such breaches is significant, as they can lead to the loss of personal data, intellectual property, and can undermine user trust in the system's security.

Model stealing: An attacker reverse-engineers a machine learning model through extensive querying, potentially exposing the model's inner workings and sensitive data used for training.

Policy Tampering: An attacker alters the access control policy, which results in falsely authorized access to the system [7].

5.2.4 Accountability threats

Accountability threats refer to challenges in identifying and holding responsible parties accountable for actions performed within the system. This includes difficulties in tracing actions back to specific users, especially in complex systems where multiple users have access to shared resources. Additionally, it involves the risk of unauthorized users performing actions without detection, thereby compromising the integrity and security of the system.

Repudiation attack: An attacker repudiates their involvement and responsibility in the system by tampering with or disabling the logs.

Impersonation attack: An attacker uses another user's credentials to access the framework and not be accountable for their actions.

5.3 Traceability through transparency

5.3.1 Distributed Ledger Technology

Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT), commonly referred to as blockchain, is a decentralized digital ledger that **records transactions** across a **network of computers**. Each block in the chain contains a cryptographic hash of the previous block, a timestamp, and transaction data. Once a block is added to the chain, it cannot be altered without changing all subsequent blocks, making the ledger of the **record transactions** tamper-evident and resistant to modification. Additionally, the **network of computers** needs to agree on a global version of the ledger, which is achieved through a consensus mechanism. This process ensures that all transactions are verified and agreed upon by the network participants before being permanently added to the blockchain. As a result, DLT provides a secure and transparent way to record transactions, ensuring that each entry is immutable and consistent across the entire network [8].

DLT is often associated with cryptocurrencies like Bitcoin [9], but it has many other potential applications beyond finance. For example, DLT can be used to create secure and transparent supply chains, track the ownership and transfer of assets, and facilitate secure data sharing between organizations.

One of the applications of DLT is the deployment of **smart contracts**, which are self-executing contracts with the terms of the agreement directly written into code. Smart contracts are deployed and executed on a DLT network, enabling trustless and transparent execution of agreements without the need for intermediaries because they operate on a decentralized system where the contract terms and transactions are distributed and auditable across multiple nodes. This decentralization ensures that no single entity controls the contract, providing a high level of security and reducing the risk of manipulation or fraud. Additionally, the immutable nature of DLT ensures that once a contract is deployed, its terms cannot be altered, fostering transparency and trust among parties. The automatic execution of these contracts upon meeting predefined conditions also eliminates the need for intermediaries, streamlining processes and reducing the potential for human error or bias.

Another application deployed in DLT is NFT, standing for Non-Fungible Token, which is a unique digital identifier that cannot be copied, substituted, or subdivided, recorded in a blockchain, and used to certify authenticity and ownership. It represents a form of a digital asset whose ownership and history are tracked. Each NFT is distinct, and unlike cryptocurrencies like Bitcoin or Ethereum, they are not interchangeable. NFTs have gained popularity, especially in the digital art world, as they provide a way to authenticate, own, and trade digital art and other assets in a secure and transparent manner.

For the ExtremeXP project, DLT and smart contracts are utilized for specific reasons:

1. **Security:** DLT provides a secure and tamper-evident way to store and manage access control policies, user attributes, and access logs. The immutability of the DLT ensures that once data is recorded, it cannot be altered, providing a high level of security and integrity for the framework.
2. **Consensus about the Data Processing Agreements (DPA):** Leveraging the decentralized verification and agreement of access control policies deploying and enforcing the DPAs rules as smart contracts by multiple stakeholders in the network. This approach ensures that policies are not only unanimously approved but also transparent and auditable, maintaining integrity and trust among all participating parties.
3. **Transparency and auditability on data processing:** The transparent nature of DLT allows for the auditing of access control decisions and data access activity. This transparency can help ensure compliance with regulations and provide a clear record of who accessed what data and when.
4. **NFT-based Data Provenance:** This mechanism utilizes NFTs to characterize datasets distinctly, providing transparent and indisputable evidence of their quality, origin, and suitability for specific analytical tasks, such as machine learning training. Integrating this approach into the framework's broader data and knowledge management lifecycle ensures that each dataset's history, including its creation, modifications, and usage, is securely recorded and easily verifiable.

5.3.2 Attribute-based Access Control based on Smart Contract

We use SmartAccess to execute an ABAC system based on Smart Contracts for ExtremeXP [10]. SmartAccess implements ABAC through smart contracts within a peer-to-peer network. Nodes in this network utilize smart contracts to set access control policies, request permissions, and verify request legitimacy. In line with XACML, 'resource' in SmartAccess refers to any data requestable, and 'target' is defined as the mix of context expression, action, and requested resource.

The XACML standard comprises five key components for access decisions: Policy Administration Point (PAP), Policy Enforcement Point (PEP), Policy Decision Point (PDP), Policy Information Point (PIP), and Context Handler (CH). PAP manages a persistent policy pool linked to target identifiers. PEP, the system's integration point, handles secure resources and processes access requests, pausing workflow

until a decision is made. It forwards requests to PDP, the central decision-making entity, which consults PIP for necessary attributes and context to evaluate policies and make decisions. PIP manages attribute values, while CH determines the request's context and, in recent developments, semantically enhances PIP's attribute values for additional context inference.

A Smart Contracts-based ABAC is essential for sharing data across organizations as it ensures transparency, compliance with regulations, and the ability to audit complex data-sharing arrangements. Traditional access control systems often fall short of securing proper data access, especially for data shared between different organizations. It facilitates a mutually agreed-upon set of access policies, dynamic control, and clear audit trails.

The European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) establishes clear guidelines for this, defining key roles such as Data Controllers, Data Processors, Data subjects and Supervisory Authorities [11]. Our ABAC based on smart contracts framework provides a practical implementation of these roles:

Data Controller: A Data Controller is an entity that determines the purposes and means of processing data, making key decisions about 'why' and 'how' data is processed. In our ABAC system based on smart contracts, the Data Controller is responsible for defining and managing the policies for data processing. This includes ensuring compliance with GDPR and overseeing the overall handling and protection of data. In cases where more than one entity is responsible for controlling the data, these entities act as **Joint Controllers** and collaboratively decide on the means and purposes of data processing, working together to manage data and to reinforce trust and effectively fulfil their distinct responsibilities.

Data Processor: A Data Processor is an entity that processes data on behalf of the Data Controller, acting under the guidelines and instructions set by the Data Controller. In our ABAC system based on smart contracts, Data Processors implement these policies through the use of smart contracts. Their role is to handle the data in accordance with the established policies, ensuring that their actions are validated against these rules, thereby maintaining the integrity and confidentiality of the data.

Data Subject: A Data Subject is any identified or identifiable natural person whose personal data is being processed. This individual is the primary focus of GDPR's protections. Within the ABAC system based on smart contracts, the Data Subject's personal data is managed and protected through the various policies and controls put in place by the Data Controllers and executed by the Data Processors.

Supervisory Authority: A Supervisory Authority is an entity that evaluates the actions of Data Controllers to ensure alignment with the regulations e.i. GDPR, Data Act etc. If a Data Controller is found to be non-compliant, the Supervisory Authority Node has the power to issue fines and enforce corrective actions, ensuring that regulatory obligations are met and maintained.

Data Storage: In our framework, efficient and secure data storage is a necessity for managing sensitive information. To address this need, we will offer a middleware that will abstract the persistence features of ExtremeXP by using a combination of peer-to-peer data-sharing approaches and traditional distributed storage solutions. This management of dataset persistence will be performed securely through the proper integration to the ExtremeXP ABAC system based on smart contracts feature.

Figure 24 Overview of our ABAC system based on smart contracts

In Figure 24, we envision the representation and the connection of the above-mentioned roles through a blockchain network with smart contracts, performing consensus mechanisms to agree on the policies and to audit the decisions made on the system. The smart contracts manage the private network and control access to off-chain resources. These four smart contracts align with the XACML model:

1. **PEPSC (Enforcement Smart Contract):** is responsible for enforcing access control policies by checking whether a user has the necessary attributes to access a particular resource. It also provides functions for logging access attempts, managing access control lists and revoking access.
2. **PDPSC (Decision Smart Contract):** is responsible for making access control decisions based on the policies defined in PAPSC and the attributes stored in PIPSC. It also includes functions for logging access control.
3. **PAPSC (Policies Administration Smart Contract):** is responsible for creating, modifying, and deleting access control policies. It also includes functions for managing policy versions, logging policy changes, and verifying policy signatures.
4. **PIPSC (Information Smart Contract):** is responsible for adding and removing nodes, retrieving public keys, and managing context attributes. It also includes functions for logging attribute changes and verifying attribute signatures.

Figure 25 A data access flow through the Smart Contracts

Figure 25 illustrates the connection between our four smart contracts and the data access flow between them. Controller nodes set and manage agreed-upon access policies for shared resources and store them in PAPSC (step 0.1). They also manage and store processor nodes' attributes in PIPSC (step 0.2). Upon receiving a data request from a processor node (step 1.1), the controller node forwards it to PEPSC (step 1.2). When PEPSC receives a request from a controller node, it sends a request for evaluation to PDPSC (step 2), which retrieves policies and attributes from PAPSC and PIPSC respectively (steps 3 and 4), evaluates, and records the decision at PEPSC (step 5). In case of permission, the processor node requests the resource off-chain through an interface from the storage node (step 6), which then gets verified by PEPSC (step 7). If verified, the storage node sends the resource to the processor node off-chain (step 8). Then, the processor node has to execute the obligations that are defined in the associated policy (step 9). Supervisory Authority nodes audit all the interaction during the data access flow. Firstly, they audit the agreed-upon policies in PAPSC (step 10.1) and the same with the attributes in PIPSC (step 10.2). They also audit the enforcement and obligations by checking the Storage nodes (step 10.3) and comparing them with decisions that were made in PEPSC (step 10.4).

In the ExtremeXP project, our use of DLT for implementing access control is tailored to suit distinct types of use cases. For scenarios that are regulated and require adherence to specific guidelines, we deploy supervisory authority nodes within our blockchain network. These nodes are crucial in scenarios where transparent policies and validation by regulatory bodies are essential. This structure ensures that all parties, including regulatory authorities, can verify and confirm that the access control

policies being used are in line with established regulations and mutually approved. This approach enhances the system's trustworthiness and accountability, ensuring that compliance with regulatory standards is maintained.

For the first type of scenario involving regulatory bodies, we could consider the example of our UC4: Flexible transportation analysis and visualization (MOBY) described in D6.1: Use case requirements. MOBY deals with regulations and has a regulatory body/Supervisory Authority since they are processing personal data. The use of our ABAC system based on smart contracts in this context ensures that the access control policies are agreed-upon regulatory standards.

On the other hand, for situations where the primary objective is to provide users with transparent logs for trust-building, in the absence of regulatory bodies, we implement joint controllers. This arrangement allows all data controllers to collectively oversee and agree upon access control policies and to diligently monitor their obligations. An example of this approach could be introduced in our UC5: Failure prevention for the manufacturing industry (IDEKO) scenario described in D6.1: Use case requirements, where the emphasis is on gaining clients' trust through clear visibility into the algorithms of the decision-making process.

In Task 5.4 of WP5, we will consider a use case-oriented approach rather than the general approach for the access control policies. We will also explore different methods for the creation and practical enforcement of obligations. We will examine the feasibility of enforcing these obligations either directly by the involved parties or through smart contracts, potentially leading to innovations within the project. Besides having enforcement, we will continue developing the obligation aspect, we will also expand the complexity of the policies to support more complex flows of the framework execution.

5.3.3 Non-Fungible Token (NFT)-based dataset provenance mechanism

In the ExtremeXP project, we adopt the concept of Non-Fungible Tokens (NFT) as a provenance mechanism for various datasets provided or generated within the ExtremeXP framework. The NFT-based Data Provenance Mechanism will be responsible for attaching a wide range of metadata (e.g., unbiased data, adequate volume, appropriate data quality etc.) on each dataset and minting them transparently and immutably, over a permissioned and private blockchain. These metadata are defined per dataset by either human evaluators or dedicated services or both, to create a trustworthy description of the datasets that can be used, through the ExtremeXP platform. Additionally, several data provenance-related information (e.g., dataset owner(s), parent dataset(s) used as input etc.) can be attached, as well.

We consider NFTs as a way to attach descriptive metadata to datasets that will be used for experiment driven analytics in a transparent, immutable and unique way defined in smart contracts. Our goal is to enhance specific datasets with metadata by multiple authorized entities in a decentralized manner for provenance, safety and auditability reasons. These metadata allow datasets to be identified, discovered and associated with specific characteristics that will be evaluated later on by data analysts who would like to explore or use it in a machine-learning experiment.

The choice of implementing an NFT-based dataset provenance approach, compared to a classic web2.0 metadata management approach, has the advantage of an immutable, transparent and safe persistence of metadata. The process involved is defined in a smart contract and the protocol implemented by the nodes participating in the blockchain network instead of being dictated by a single server.

We have designed and implemented a decentralized prototype application based on a smart contract that defines a process for creating ("minting" is the common term for creating a new NFT token) a new unique token representing a dataset when specific requirements are met. In the case of ExtremeXP this involves a specific number of attributes, defined by data engineers, which are evaluated by multiple authorized entities participating in the blockchain network. When the

evaluation process is complete, the dataset owner can mint the uniquely identified NFT. All the information associated with this unique object is stored on chain and the whole minting process is transparent to everyone participating in the network. Whenever a transaction, that changes the “state” of the blockchain network, takes places, appropriate messages (events in the “smart-contract” world) are generated and broadcasted among the nodes of the network, so that the corresponding actions regarding the application interaction can be made. In our case, this involves informing the users through a UI about the actions made. The following sequence diagram (Figure 26) illustrates the implemented approach for minting an NFT.

The Dataset Creator requests access to mint an NFT. The ABAC mechanism is invoked through an API call and returns the authorization result. If authorization is granted, they upload the dataset itself and retrieve the corresponding URI (Uniform Resource Identifier). As a next step, they interact with the ExtremeXP Provenance smart contract and calls the add function by providing the URI as argument. This function call actually initializes a new structure in the smart contract for the uploaded dataset, within which any metadata is stored. As soon as the transaction gets confirmed on the blockchain network, an event message is broadcasted and returned to the dataset creator, as well as to the Dataset Reviewers (Humans: $H_1...H_N$ and Services: $S_1...S_N$) through the ExtremeXP platform. Afterwards, dataset reviewers interact with the ExtremeXP UI and request access to evaluate a dataset. The ABAC mechanism is invoked again through an API call and returns the authorization result. If authorization is granted, reviewers provide their evaluation values for the attributes they are authorized to evaluate. Every time a new evaluation is added, an event message is emitted, and all parties get informed about it. When the evaluation is complete, the data owner can mint the NFT for the uploaded dataset. A final event message is emitted, and all parties get informed about the creation of the new NFT.

Figure 26 Overview of the NFT-based provenance mechanism - Minting an NFT

As an alternative to this approach, we have experimented with a second prototype application based on a smart contract emulating an auction, inspired by the corresponding well-defined smart contracts in the public DLTs (e.g., on NFT-based artwork auctions). According to this implementation once the dataset has been uploaded, an associate NFT is minted pertaining metadata like its hash/URI, the URIs (if any) of its parent datasets from which it has been produced, its owner(s), etc. After the minting takes place the auctioning phase is initiated. We consider data engineers as “bidders”, who can participate in the auction as authorized entities to evaluate some attributes of the datasets. Moreover, we consider their “bids” as the corresponding values of their evaluations with respect to specific dataset metadata. This approach has the advantage of gas efficiency compared to the first approach. However, some initial assumptions and validations are needed regarding the bids and their meaning. Both approaches are implemented using ERC721 as a base NFT contract, extended with enumerable or URI storage functionalities provided by OpenZeppelin libraries [12]. The sequence diagram, below (Figure 27), illustrates the described approach for minting an NFT.

Figure 27 Overview of the NFT-Auction-based provenance mechanism - Minting an NFT

As in the first approach, the Dataset Creator interacts with the ExtremeXP UI and requests access to mint an NFT. The ABAC mechanism is invoked through an API call and returns the authorization result. If authorization is granted, they upload the dataset itself as well as the associated metadata and retrieves the corresponding URIs (Uniform Resource Identifiers). Then, they interact with the ExtremeXP Provenance smart contract and call the mint function by providing the URIs as arguments. When the NFT is minted, an event message is broadcasted and returned to the dataset creator, as well as to the Dataset Reviewers (Humans: H₁...H_n and Services: S₁...S_n) through the Extreme-XP platform. Once this step is completed, the bidding phase starts, in which the evaluators interact with the ExtremeXP UI and request access to evaluate a dataset. The ABAC mechanism is invoked again through an API call and returns the authorization result. If authorization is granted, reviewers make their bids for the auction. When the auction is complete, an event message is again emitted, and all parties get informed about the end of the dataset evaluation.

We note that in all of the above diagrams, domain experts are involved as part of the (human) dataset reviewer role. Their interactions in terms of these sequence diagrams is important as they are capable of (immutably) characterising important aspects of datasets managed by the ExtremeXP platform. As

far as the retrieval of a dataset is concerned, the process is demonstrated in the next sequence diagram (Figure 28).

Figure 28 Overview of the NFT-based provenance mechanism – Retrieving a Dataset

At first, a domain expert or a data analyst interacts with Extreme XP UI and requests a Dataset or a list of Datasets. As always, the ABAC mechanism is invoked through an API call and returns the authorization result. If authorization is granted, the associated metadata and provenance information are resolved and returned through the Extreme XP framework. As a final step, the user requests to get access to the desired dataset and retrieves it from the decentralized storage component. The process is almost common for the second approach. It involves one more call for retrieving bidders from the smart contract for the requested NFT, as shown in the next figure (Figure 29).

Figure 29 Overview of the NFT-Auction-based provenance mechanism – Retrieving a Dataset

6 Framework Architecture

The section describes the architecture of the ExtremeXP framework. As already introduced in Section 2, the ExtremeXP framework is a collection of interacting software components and repositories provided by the ExtremeXP partners. The four high-level framework modules (FM) are (Section 2.3):

1. **FM1 - Experiment Modeling**
2. **FM2 - Experiment Execution**
3. **FM3 - User Interaction**
4. **FM4 - Knowledge Management**

Here, we will delve into the details of each module. We will describe the architecture both from a structural perspective, i.e., which components and repositories belong to each module, and from a behavioural/interaction perspective, i.e., how users interact with each module and how components within each module interact with each other and with components in other modules.

We note that this is a *reference architecture* for the ExtremeXP use cases. It consists of *conceptual* components that embody the different functionalities supported by the ExtremeXP framework: specifying and planning experiments, scheduling, and monitoring complex analytic workflows (CAWs), managing data and access to knowledge assets, interacting with users, etc. Each conceptual component can be in principle reified by one or more different *technical* components. Whereas the choice of concrete technical components depends on the constraints and deployment environment of each use case, we expect that several technical components will be reused across use cases.

6.1 User roles in ExtremeXP framework

It is also important to mention upfront that the ExtremeXP framework (and, by extension, its architecture) caters to the needs of users that have different roles, namely:

- **Data engineer.** Needs to run one or more experiments to develop optimized and trustworthy CAWs. Data engineers realize the requirements of domain experts by specifying experiments, specifying access control processes, and controlling the execution of experiments.
- **Domain expert.** Provides the requirements for the experiments to be specified and run (e.g. which CAW workflow to be optimized, which metrics to use in doing so), consumes the results of the CAW (including the visualization and explainability ones), needs to trust the experimentation process followed by the framework.
- **Data creator:** Provides the datasets acting as inputs to the CAWs involved in the experiments; has certain privacy and confidentiality requirements that need to be preserved during the experimentation process.

6.2 Structural perspective

To address the diverse needs of these users, several functional blocks have been identified, designed as software components with clear responsibilities, and assembled to constitute the four main modules of the ExtremeXP framework. For each component, an ExtremeXP partner is responsible for gathering input from the other partners (e.g., requirements/designs/implementations) with respect to each component and providing both intermediary and a final version of the component to be integrated in the overall framework. Table 8 and Figure 30 give an overview of the different components covering their names and a short description of their responsibilities. These figures also provide an overview of the framework architecture from a structural perspective.

Figure 30 Structural view of ExtremeXP framework architecture.

Table 8 Overview of ExtremeXP components.

Module name	Component name	Component description	Responsible partner
Experiment Modeling	Experiments Editor	Enables data engineers to specify experiments via textual and/or graphical editors. Specifications need to follow the ExtremeXP meta-model described in Section 3. Candidate technologies for implementing this component are EMF and React (for the graphical editor part).	VUA
	Intent Specification Editor and Experiments Generator	Enables data engineers to specify intents and translates those intents into full experiment specifications. As for the Experiments editor, the generated specifications need to follow the ExtremeXP meta-model described in Section 3. An initial prototype for this component is based at https://github.com/dtim-upc/IntentSpecification2WorkflowGenerator	UPC
	Analytic Tasks Library	Provides predefined analytic tasks corresponding to common tasks such as data discovery and integration, and model or feature selection. The tasks can be selected by data engineers using the Experiments Editor and/or the Intent Specification Editor and Experiments Generator, configured to match the needs of the CAW, and added to the experiment/intent specifications. The tasks that populate the library are the technical outcomes of WP3 of ExtremeXP.	TUD

	Design Model Storage	Stores the specification artifacts of experiments and/or intents while these are developed by the data engineers using the Experiments Editor and/or the Intent Specification Editor and Experiments Generator, respectively. These artifacts are updatable, but not necessarily versioned. A candidate technology for implementing/reifying this component is EMF.cloud; however, the file system can also be used for storing design models in a first prototype.	VUA
Experiment Execution	Experimentation Engine	Orchestrates the execution of experiments as specified by their models. Depending on each experiment's attributes, uses different execution strategies that prescribe, e.g., the sequential/parallel execution of CAWs or utilize optimization algorithms to select the next CAW to run based on the result of previous executions. To run a CAW, it invokes the Executionware. While selecting CAWs to run, it may also consult the Options Explorer. An initial implementation of this component will be based on the Real-Time Experimentation (RTX) Python tool.	VUA
	Options Explorer	Supports the decision-making of the optimization algorithms hosted by the Experimentation Engine (and/or of the data engineers controlling a running experiment) on which CAW variants to run and in which order. Based on knowledge from past experiments, it predicts which CAW variants are more promising to run, hence effectively limiting the variability space of an experiment and speeding up its overall execution. Markov Decision Model and Bayesian Networks are expected to be trained/calibrated and hosted within this software component to enable decision making.	UL
	Executionware	Executes a CAW by executing all its steps. For each step, the necessary input datasets are requested by the Knowledge Management module, and the produced output datasets (including metrics used for evaluating the CAW) are persisted via Knowledge Management. The execution progress is periodically reported back to the Experimentation Engine.	AE
User Interaction	Visualization Meta-model	The Visualization Meta-model provides means for specifying a visualization to be used in an experiment in a declarative way. It is also possible	SIN

		to use an existing module outside the experiment engine for visualizations in an experiment.	
Visual explainability		If there are explanations available as part of an experiment, these are presented as part of the visualizations in an experiment.	SIN
Visualization Toolkit		The Visualization Toolkit provides means for executing a visualization.	SIN
UI Interactor		Facilitates user interaction with the visualization, while also capturing and processing these interactions for further system response.	SIN
Visual Operation Evaluation Engine		Evaluates user interactions from the visualization interface, translating them into visualization and explainability actions and queries, and then integrates the results back to the UI.	ARC
Prefetching Engine		The Prefetching Engine anticipates data requirements based on user interactions and system patterns, fetching data in advance to reduce latency and improve user experience.	ARC
Visualization Query Optimizer		Optimizes queries for data visualization using techniques like aggregation and sampling, ensuring efficient data retrieval and processing while meeting user requirements for latency and accuracy in the visualization output.	ARC
Cache Manager		Manages the caching of frequently accessed data and results, reducing the need for repeated queries and reducing the latency of the visualization.	ARC
Explainability Executor		This component orchestrates the execution of explainability methods, managing the workflow and resources needed to generate explanations for model decisions.	ARC
Explainability Methods Repository		A repository of various explainability algorithms and methods, allowing for the selection and application of appropriate techniques based on the specific explainability requirements of an experiment.	ARC
Surrogate Models Training		Trains surrogate models for generating explanations and modeling the measured objective based on hyper-parameterization and preprocessing configurations. These models serve as proxies to understand the relationships between parameters and ML model behaviour/performance.	ARC

Knowledge Management	Dataset Catalog	Stores metadata regarding the datasets that either provided to or generated by experiments in the framework. Such metadata include the location of the dataset (in the Distributed File System Management), provenance and ownership information (important for access control), and also pointers to the deployed CAWs and their runs and associated parameters (in the Model Repository). All these information aim to provide complete traceability of experiment results.	CUNI
	Model Repository	Stores the specifications (including CAWs, metrics, variability points, constraints), in the form of serialized models, of experiments executed via the Experiment Execution module. Such models are immutable, so that traceability can be always provided to experiment results, and versioned, so that several runs of the same experiment specification can be performed. Candidate technologies for this component are document databases and search engines like Elasticsearch.	CUNI
	NFT-based Data Provenance	Tags with metadata any input datasets used for experiment-driven analytics in ExtremeXP in a transparent, immutable, and unique manner. Through this mechanism any such dataset can be characterized according to a wide range of metadata (e.g., unbiased, adequate volume, appropriate quality etc.) by expert human evaluators or services. Along these characteristics, information such as dataset owner(s) and parent dataset(s) used, will be attached/minted as Non-Fungible Tokens (NFT) over a permissioned and private blockchain.	ICCS
	Access Control	Manages user permissions across various modules. It enforces attribute-based access control (ABAC) for interacting with key components like the Dataset Catalog, Model Repository, and NFT-based Data Provenance. This component ensures secure access to datasets, experiment specifications, and metrics, maintaining data integrity and confidentiality. Its integration with distributed file systems and DLT enhances security, supports data provenance, and guarantees traceability, aligning with the goal of secure, transparent access in a decentralized environment.	TUD

	Distributed File System Management	Manages decentralized data and knowledge artefacts related to ExtremeXP experiments. Specifically, any input datasets to be used in experiments or their outputs, considered as output datasets, will be persisted using a combination of peer-to-peer data sharing approaches and traditional distributed storage solutions. Last, the management of datasets will be performed in a secure manner through the proper integration to the ExtremeXP ABAC authorization feature.	ICCS
	Metrics Management	Stores the metrics generated by performing experiments and, consequently, running CAWs. Each CAW task can potentially provide a metric (e.g., accuracy, execution time) as an output. Candidate technologies for this component are timeseries and more generally NoSQL databases and solution such as ElasticSearch, TimeScaleDB and Prometheus.	CUNI

6.3 Behavioural perspective

To provide a behaviour/interactions perspective, we will zoom into each module in turn in the rest of this section.

6.3.1 FM1 – Experiment Modeling

The internal and external interactions of the components included in the Experiment Modeling module are depicted in Figure 31 and described next.

Figure 31 Interactions of the Experiment Modeling module.

1. The data engineer receives the requirements from the domain expert and specifies experiment models. To do so, they can use either the Experiments Editor or the Intent Specification Editor and Experiments Generator.
2. The Experiments Editor is used for specifying experiments. In particular, the data engineer using a textual and/or graphical editor produces a number of experiment specification artifacts, i.e., models that need to follow the ExtremeXP meta-model and stores them in the Design Model Storage. While specifying experiments, the data engineer can select and configure tasks from the Analytic Tasks Library.
3. The Intent Specification Editor and Experiments Generator (a web application with a graphical interface) is used for specifying intents. These intents are automatically transformed into experiment models that follow the ExtremeXP meta-model and saved into the Design Model Storage. The data engineer can also select and configure tasks from the Analytic Tasks Library.
4. Before using the Experiment Editor and the Intent Specification Editor and Experiments Generator, the data engineer needs to authenticate (not shown in the figure). After doing so,

their (read/write/access) access to models via the Experiments Editor and the Intent Specification Editor and Experiments Generator is controlled by the Access Control component.

- The experiment models are retrieved from the Analytic Tasks Library and provided to the Experimentation Engine of the Experiment Execution (Section 6.3.2).

6.3.2 FM2 – Experiment Execution

The internal and external interactions of the components included in the Experiment Execution module are depicted in Figure 32 and described next.

Figure 32 Interactions of the Experiment Execution module.

- The Experimentation Engine receives an experiment specification to be orchestrated and executed. From the user's perspective (not shown in the figure), this may happen via, e.g., clicking a button on the Experiments Editor or the Intent Specification Editor and Experiments Generator of Experiment Modeling. The data engineer starts a new experiment at this initial step by providing the corresponding experiment models from the Design Model Storage.
- The Experimentation Engine creates concrete Complex Analytics Workflows (CAWs) and provides them to the Executionware. CAWs can be provided one-by-one or in bulk; we will assume the former for the rest of this process description.
- The Executionware executes the CAWs by running its tasks in the specified order. For each task, it retrieves the input datasets from the Dataset Catalog (3.1), executes it, and produces its output datasets, including the relevant metrics. If the task involves obtaining user metrics, it receives them from the User Interaction module (3.2). It also sends progress messages back to the Experimentation Engine in predefined execution points (e.g., after the execution of each task, in periodic intervals) (3.3). Finally, all the produced datasets and metrics are saved in the Dataset Catalog (3.4).
- After the execution of a CAW, its metrics are sent to the Experimentation Engine so that the next CAW(s) selection is informed.

5. To decide on the next CAW to be executed, the Experimentation Engine can request a recommendation from the Options Explorer. This step only takes place in context-driven experiments (Section 2.1.1).
6. After the execution of all the CAWs in an experiment, the experiment model is persisted in the Model Repository.
7. At several points in the above process, when access is needed to the actual datasets and their metadata, related access requests from (authenticated) users have to be granted by the Access Control component of Knowledge Management.
8. Users should be able to interfere with a running experiment to pause/resume and stop it. We also envision more complicated interactions that involve changing the underlying CAW of experiments (enabling Open experiments – Section 2.1.1). For now, such interactions are planned to take place via the User Interaction module.

6.3.3 FM3 – User Interaction

The internal and external interactions of the components included in the User Interaction module are depicted in Figure 33 and described next.

1. The User (acting in the role of Data Engineer or Domain Expert) interacts with Visualization Middleware via the User Interface components.
2. The Visual Operation Evaluation Engine evaluates the visualization and explainability request received by the user. It first asks the Visualization Query Optimizer to optimize the visualization query considering the user constraints and intents (e.g. use sampling or aggregation) (2.1). It then checks, via the Cache Manager, whether the necessary data are already cached (2.2). If not, the Dataset Catalog provides them to the Cache Manager (2.3). The Access Control component is used to evaluate whether the (authenticated) user has access to the requested datasets (2.4).
3. If explainability aspects are requested by the user in step 1, an explainability request is sent from the Visual Operation Evaluation Engine to the Explainability Executor. The latter then in turn selects the appropriate explainability method to run from the Explainability Models Repository (3.1), trains a surrogate model (if needed) (3.2), runs the explainability method, and returns its results to the Visual Operation Evaluation Engine (3.3).
4. The Visual Operation Evaluation Engine combines the visualization and explainability results.
5. As an extra performance-enhancing step, the Visual Operation Evaluation Engine may ask the Prefetching Engine for prefetching data for future visualization and explainability requests.
6. Finally, the Visual Operation Evaluation Engine sends the combined visualization and explainability results to the User Interface components.

Figure 33 Interactions of the User Interaction module.

6.3.4 FM4 – Knowledge Management

The internal and external interactions of the components included in the Knowledge Management module are depicted in Figure 34 and described next.

Figure 34 Interactions of the Knowledge Management module.

The Knowledge Management module can be seen as a set of services of the ExtremeXP framework that enable the persistence and privacy-preserving storage and access of data from the framework. Since we have already detailed all the interactions of Knowledge Management with the components of the other three modules in the previous sections, we focus here on the interactions that take place within the module itself.

1. As an initial step in executing any experiment or workflow in the framework, the Data Creator needs to provide the necessary input datasets.
2. As a second necessary step, the Data Engineer needs to specify data access policies to the datasets uploaded from step 1, but also to the datasets created via the framework itself.

3. One of the main responsibilities of the Knowledge Management module is to provide secure access to the datasets to the users that have access to them and only to these users. This is the main functionality of the Access Control component, which essentially enforces the data access policies specified by the Data Engineer in step 2. Specifically, these policies may refer to multiple contextual attributes (e.g., role, time of request, location of the requestor etc.) that should be evaluated before yielding an access control decision. In particular, the Access Control yields permit/deny decisions whenever a user tries to access either a dataset from the Distributed File System Management component (3.1) or from the Metrics Management component (3.2).
4. Any dataset available through the ExtremeXP distributed file system can have several metadata (i.e., characteristics) attached to it. These characteristics are defined per dataset by either human evaluators or dedicated services or both, in order to create a trustworthy description of the datasets that can be used, through the platform. The NFT-based Data Provenance Mechanism [4] will be responsible for attaching a wide range of metadata (e.g., unbiased data, adequate volume, appropriate data quality etc.) on each dataset and minting them transparently and immutably, over a permissioned and private blockchain. In addition, several data provenance-related information (e.g., dataset owner(s), parent dataset(s) used as input etc.) can be attached, as well.

7 Conclusion

This deliverable contains the initial architecture of the ExtremeXP framework, as well as initial design of the meta-models, DSML and context representation. Its architecture aims at achieving its human-in-the-loop and fit-for-purpose approach in the design and operation of Complex Analytics Workflows.

The main achievements of this work are the following:

- Detailed analysis of the use cases and their requirements that fed the design of the ExtremeXP framework architecture.
- Definition of all main concepts in the meta-model. Its components can be used to initialize and start filling in the ExtremeXP knowledge base of experiments.
- Definition and initial evaluation of supporting probabilistic processes, such as Markov Decision Model and Bayesian Network.
- Design and experimentation with an initial blockchain-based ABAC approach for the ExtremeXP knowledge base.
- Initial structural and behavioral representation of the ExtremeXP framework architecture.

Following the delivery of the initial architecture, language models and core functionalities, the WPs 3-5 will consider the optimal possible implementation approach. Following its delivery at M12, the deliverable D2.1 will continue to evolve by considering the results of WPs 3-5. The final framework architecture, as well as the details on the distributed ledger methods will be delivered in M36 as part of D2.2.

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